

Project Title	Sustainable Social Grocery Stores
Status	Returned for revision
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Applicant Status	Staff (Senior Lecturer in Human Resources and Organisational Behaviour)
Department	Management
Project Start Date	27-Feb-2022
Project End Date	31-Jan-2023
External Funding in place	Yes
External Collaborators	Yes
Funder/Project Title	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council - Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvant
Name of Funder	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council

Ethical Review Application ER/ES483/5 (continued)

Project Description

This study 'Sustainable social grocery stores: Seeking the 'social' behind the market' seeks to better understand the community concerns and needs of young people accessing a social grocery store which provides low cost subsidised food parcels. It forms part of a larger project investigating young peoples' understandings of and relationships with food. Participants will be identified by the Youth Advice Centre (YAC) with whom we have established relationships and recruited on the basis of expressing an interest in the study, having received support with food via this organisation over the last two years, and between the ages of 16-25. The initial phase of the research will draw upon surveys in order to better understand the food seeking behaviour and experiences of people aged 16-25 living within Brighton and Hove who are accessing, or wanting to access, food through the YAC Food Market. Thereafter, the research will identify self-selecting key participants who will be invited for one-to-one interviews to discuss their views on food and their food seeking experiences further. Where appropriate, the research will draw upon arts-based methods whereby a range of creative prompts will be draw upon in order to explore young peoples' food practices, access, understandings and aspirations.

The study is part of a wider project funded by the UKRI. The Research team at Sussex will focus specifically on communities in Tower Hamlets in London and Brighton and Hove, working alongside of WEN, the women's environmental network and BHFP, Brighton and Hove Food Partnership. In addition, we will be studying how policies inflect and constraint food access, supply and sustainability. The larger project is described as follows: Preliminary work has shown that people living in disadvantaged communities have the desire to eat a healthier diet and are aware that good nutrition is closely linked to good physical and mental health. This project will focus on sharing knowledge and learning from working with: people from a variety of disadvantaged communities Whitley-Reading Brighton & Hove Tower Hamlets Plymouth small and large food businesses policy-makers. This will help develop solutions that will provide people living in disadvantaged communities with improved access to fresher food and a balance of desirable, sustainable, affordable and healthy products. It will identify opportunities to prevent food loss from 'mainstream' supply chains and identify where increased sustainable production of primary food ingredients is needed.

The project will utilise co-design, co-production and participatory methods that enable major food businesses and community owned enterprises to engage with each other, and with the citizens who consume food. The project is split into three phases: · Phase 1 will build a picture of the national food landscape in disadvantaged communities and evaluate current corporate, social and government policy frameworks that guide food and agriculture · Phase 2 will bring together communities and businesses to codevelop new supply chains, food products and policy frameworks · Phase 3 will assess the impact of scaling these innovations to national level and quantify the potential impact of these changes on the environment and health.

Ethical Review Form Section A (ER/ES483/5)	
Question	Response
>> Checklist	
A1. Will your study involve participants who are currently or potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position (e.g. people under 18, people with learning difficulties, over-researched groups or people in care facilities)?	Yes
A2. Will participants be required to take part in the study without their consent or knowledge at the time (e.g. covert observation of people in non-public places), and / or will deception of any sort be used? Please refer to the British Psychological Society Code of Ethics and Conduct (or similar guidelines) for further information.	No
A3. Unless specifically and clearly consented (e.g. a media release form), will it be possible, through a research output, to identify participants in any way? (This does not include taking email details for participant prize draws or identifying participants from signed consent forms or holding identity encryption spreadsheets that are stored securely separate from the research data).	No
A4. Might the study induce psychological stress or anxiety, or produce humiliation or cause harm or negative consequences beyond the risks likely to be encountered in the everyday life of the participants?	No
A5. Is there a risk that the research topic might lead to disclosures from the participant concerning their beliefs, involvement in illegal actions or any other activities that may represent a threat to themselves or others?	No
A6. Will the study involve collecting any personal special category information* in a form that could allow the participant/ participants to be identified? [* identifiers relating to race, ethnic origin, politics, religion, trade union membership, philosophical beliefs, genetics, biometrics, health, sex life or sexual orientation]	Yes
A7. Will any drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) be administered as part of this study and will any invasive or potentially harmful procedures of any kind will be used?	No
A8. Will your project involve working with any substances and / or equipment which may be considered hazardous?	No
A9. Will your study involve the taking and/or storage of human tissue that falls under the Human Tissue Act (HTA)? http://www.sussex.ac.uk/staff/research/governance/erp_overview/humantissue	No
>> Risk Assessment	
A10. If you have answered Yes to ANY of the above questions, your application may be considered as HIGH risk. If, however you wish to make a case that your application should be considered as LOW risk please enter the reasons here. Researchers should note that SREOs or C-RECs may decide NOT to agree with the case that you have made.	

Ethical Review Form Section C (ER/ES483/5)	
Question	Response
>> Risk Checklist - Participants	
C1. Is DBS (Disclosure and Barring Service) clearance necessary for this project? If yes, please ensure you complete Section C24a below	Yes
C2. Are alcoholic drinks, drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) to be administered to the study participants?	No

C3. Can you think of anything else that might be potentially harmful to participants in this research?

There is potential for participants to experience some anxiety or stress about their food practices and understandings through the course of the research. The researchers are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, for the wellbeing of both parties. The initial survey will identify participants who are volunteering to discuss their experiences further and will help provide an insight into topics of importance for interviews. By employing an open structure to interviews, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. Given that existing relationship with YAC, all participants will be directed towards appropriate support services, should anything arise within interviews that may be distressing for participants. This includes but is not limited to: Access to emergency food provision; support with eating disorders and support with mental illness. The researcher and local gatekeeper are aware of organisations which could provide further help in the region should signposting be required (e.g. Eating Disorder Hope; BEAT, Mind).

C4. Does the project involve working with any substances and/or equipment which may be considered hazardous? (Please refer to the University's Control of Hazardous Substances Policy http://www.sussex.ac.uk/hso/policies).	No
C5. Could the nature or subject of the research potentially have an emotionally disturbing impact on the researcher(s)?	No
C5a. If yes, briefly describe what measures will be taken to help the researcher(s) to manage this.	
C6. Could the nature or subject of the research potentially expose the researcher(s) to threats of physical violence and / or verbal abuse?	No
C6a. If yes, briefly describe what measures will be taken to mitigate this.	
C7. Does the research involve any fieldwork - Overseas or in the UK?	Yes
C7a. If yes, where will the fieldwork take place? (All research requiring overseas travel will require the submission of a fully completed OTTSRA form). In the event that the Foreign and Commonwealth Office has travel warnings in place for the country (ies) to be visited you will also need to provide a detailed risk assessment.	The fieldwork will take place in Brighton in a Youth Club social food market.
C8. Will any researchers be in a lone working situation?	Yes
C8a. If yes, briefly describe the location, time of day and duration of lone working. What precautionary measures will be taken to ensure safety of the researcher(s)?	The studies will be carried out in the YAC premises in central Brighton, in a semi-public venue during usual daytime working hours in a place one of the researchers doing the fieldwork is very familiar with.
C9. Can you think of anything else that might be potentially harmful to the researcher(s) in this research?	
>> Data Collection and Analysis (Please provide full details)	

C10. PARTICIPANTS: How many people do you envisage will participate, who are they, and how will they be selected?

C10: Participants will be selected on the basis of having received, in some capacity, support with food provision from YAC. All participants must have opted in to be involved with the study. We are aiming to recruit participants aged between 16-25, across a mix of genders and ethnicities, where possible. If any participants are under the age of 16 we will request consent from guardians. We will aim for 30 survey responses and 10 interviews but this might change slightly depending on local interest in the project. A token of appreciation will be given in the form of a voucher. We will liaise with the rest of the UKRI project team to identify comparable recompense in similar methods.

C11. RECRUITMENT: How will participants be approached and recruited?

Potential participants will be identified by YAC who will share the project information sheet with young people involved in accessing their food market. After understanding the voluntary nature of the research, potential participants will be invited to engage in a 10 minute anonymous survey using Qualtrics and provided with computer access at the YAC premises to fill this in. After the survey, participants will be invited by our local gatekeeper to express their interest in engaging with a one-to-one interview at the YAC premises. Young people interested in being interviewed will be introduced to the researcher by the YAC gatekeeper and the researcher will explain informed consent and go through the information sheet with prospective key participants to make sure they fully understand the implications of being involved. As such, all participants will be recruited on the basis of having expressed an interest in engaging in the study and with an understanding of the research project. Participants will be offered a shopping voucher as recompense/remuneration participating in the interview and survey. The exact amount of the voucher needs to be agreed with other universities participating in the UKRI project and

Sussex guidelines.

<p>C12. METHOD: What research method(s) do you plan to use; e.g. interview, questionnaire/self-completion questionnaire, field observation, audio/audio-visual recording etc.?</p>	<p>The project will draw upon a survey via Qualtrics and one-to-one interviews to explore young peoples' relationships with and experiences of accessing food within their local communities. While the preferred method of interviews is face to face, if appropriate given the context of COVID-19, participants will have the opportunity of being interviewed via zoom. The researcher will also make select visits to the site of the food market, in order to take field notes and observations that will form part of the analysis. We have not submitted an observation consent form as our observations will be brief due to the nature of transactions in the market. We hope to be unobtrusive and felt that asking people to sign a consent form could feel intrusive in this context. We will be observing shopping practices and interactions.</p>
<p>C13. LOCATION: Where will the project be carried out e.g. public place, in researcher's office, in private office at organisation?</p>	<p>C13: The studies will be carried out in the YAC premises in central Brighton, in a semi-public venue during usual daytime working hours.</p>
<p>>> Ethical Considerations (Please provide full details)</p>	

C14. PARTICIPANT WELLBEING: Will the study involve engaging participants in the discussion of distressing or sensitive topics? (e.g. sexual activity, drug use, ethnicity, political behaviour, potentially illegal activities). If so, please set out how you will manage the well-being of participants.

C14: Participants, including potentially young people will be asked to discuss their relationship to food via surveys and interviews. There is the possibility that this could raise some anxiety or distress. We will make clear that participants can end the survey at any point should they wish, and they will be accessing this survey within the YAC centre, whereby there is an existing support structure in place as well as the potential of signposting for additional support services where appropriate. Before conducting interviews, we will take extra steps explaining the study via information sheets distributed and will emphasise that participants can withdraw their involvement should they wish during an interview, or up to two weeks after an interview has taken place

C15. INFORMED CONSENT: Please describe the process you will use to ensure your participants are freely giving fully informed consent to participate. This will usually include the provision of an Information Sheet and will normally require a Consent Form unless there is justification for not doing so. (Please state this clearly).

C15: Informed consent will be sought through the provision of an information sheet, verbal explanation of the project to participants and a consent form and information sheet for any participants under the age of 16. For the purpose of the survey, a summary explaining the aims of the study and the voluntary nature of engagement will be provided before any survey questions are asked. For the purpose of interviews, the information provided will consist of an explicit invitation to participate in the study, the purpose of the study, and the way in which possible participants will be asked to engage. The researcher will make themselves available to discuss any potential concerns participants or their guardians may have as well as their right to not be included in the study or in any of the select site observations made by the researcher.

C16. RIGHT OF WITHDRAWAL: Participants should be able to withdraw from the research at any time. Participants should also be able to withdraw their data if it is linked to them and should be told when this will no longer be possible (e.g. once it has been included in the final report). Please describe the exact arrangements for withdrawal from participation and withdrawal of data for your study.

C16: Participants will be able to withdraw at any point within interviews themselves, without having to provide any explanation. They will also be able to withdraw from the study up until two weeks after data collection has occurred. This information will form part of the information sheet and discussion. Participants can stop the survey at any point and are under no obligation to complete it should they prefer not to do so.

C17. OTHER ETHICAL ISSUES: If you answered YES to anything in A.1 above (participants who are potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position) you must specifically address this here. Please also consider whether there are other ethical issues you should be covering here. Please also refer to the professional code of conduct you intend to follow in your research.

C17: As the research is focused upon young peoples' relationships with and understandings of food and experiences of accessing food, it is possible that the discussions themselves might raise topics that are potentially emotionally difficult or sensitive for the participants. The researcher has experience of working and researching within socially deprived environments and is particularly sensitive to the potential vulnerabilities of participants. The researcher has received training in counselling skills and are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, for the wellbeing of both parties. The researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. As reflexivity is of the utmost importance throughout the research process, the researcher will maintain a research diary where they explore ethical issues as they arise and which will serve as a means for them to constantly reflect upon the research process and to share these reflections with colleagues in the research team.

>> Data Protection, Confidentiality, and Records Management	
C18. DPA: Will you ensure that the processing of personal information related to the study will be in full compliance with the Data Protection Act 2018 (GDPR)? Please give full details under C19a. (http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa)	Yes
C18a. If you are processing any personal information outside of the European Economic Area (EEA) you must explain how compliance with the Data Protection Act 2018 (GDPR) will be ensured. http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa/transfersoutsideeea	
C19. CONFIDENTIALITY: Will you take steps to ensure the confidentiality of personal information? Please explain how any identifiable personal records and research data will be managed and stored whilst ensuring that participants have given appropriate informed consent for this in C19a and or C20 below.	Yes

C19a. DATA MANAGEMENT: Please provide details of any anonymisation procedures and of physical and technical security measures (including secure storage) of identifiable personal and research data here. Indicate how these will be employed in the collection, analysis and research output and dissemination stages.

C19a: The names of all participants in the study will be anonymised in order to protect their identities, as will the name of the community centre with which they are associated. Surveys will be taken using the Sussex approved password protected platform Qualtrics. All data will be managed by the researcher and securely stored and transferred using Sussex Box. Project passwords will be pre-set and will contain a combination of at least eight alphanumeric and symbolic characters. Once uploaded to Box, original copies of data will be securely deleted from local storage locations. The shared project workspace on Box will be maintained, organised and updated by the researcher, who will do weekly checks on version control, archiving, monitoring and tidying. All raw data files will be named with anonymous unique IDs and a password-protected database will keep record of links between unique IDs and personal data. Shared folders containing raw data will have access limited to the research team.

C20. CONSENT: If personal information related to this study will be retained and shared (i.e. in outputs) in a form that is not fully anonymised (separated from information that can identify the participant) please outline how participants will be made aware of this (including any limitations) and indicate their consent.	
C21. Will the Principal Investigator take full responsibility during the study, for ensuring appropriate storage and security of information (including research data, consent forms and administrative records) and, where appropriate, will the necessary arrangements be made in order to process copyright material lawfully?	Yes
C21a. If you answered "No" to the above question, please give further details of how data and records will be managed:	
C22. Who will have access to personal information and data relating to this study?	The two researchers named on the ethics submission and the project administrator.
C23. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN: AFTER the study: State how long study information including research data, consent forms and personal identification will be retained, in what format(s) and where the information will be kept. http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/recordsmanagementguidance	At the end of the project in 2026 the PI will collect all relevant documentation together and store physical and electronic documents securely. The data will be kept until 2030.
>> Other Ethical Clearances and Permissions	
C24. Are any other ethical clearances or permissions (internal or external) required? Please see the help text (i) for further details.	No
C24a. If yes, please give further details including the name and address of the organisation. If other ethical approval has already been received please attach evidence of approval, otherwise you will need to supply it when ready. (You do not need to provide evidence of a current DBS check at this point).	

Survey questions

This research is seeking to better understand the food seeking behaviour and experiences of people aged 16-25 living within Brighton and Hove who are accessing, or wanting to access, food through the YAC Food Market.

The research has received ethical approval from the University of Sussex Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee. By taking part in the survey, you are consenting for your responses to be analysed as part of the research project. All responses to this survey are anonymous and participation in this research is entirely voluntary. If you have any questions about the research please get in touch: e.swan@sussex.ac.uk or f.mazanderani@sussex.ac.uk

We estimate that it will take approximately 10 minutes to answer the questions below:

What is your age?

What gender do you most identify with?

Please self-identify

What ethnic group do you most identify with?

Please self-identify

Do you buy food just for yourself or for others?

For myself

For myself and other

If yes, who else do you buy food for?

Where do you normally access your food from?

Supermarket (Which ones?)

Family members/friends

Foodbank/food hub

Other (please specify)

Please indicate how important the following are to you when purchasing food:

Likert scale – Very important to not important

The cost of the food

How 'healthy' the food is

How 'environmentally sustainable' the food is

How easy the food is to cook or prepare

How much you enjoy the food

How much others will enjoy the food (if buying for others)

What food items that you would like to see in a food shop from YAC? Please tick all that apply and provide further information if you would like)

Tinned beans/legumes

Tinned tomatoes

Baked beans

Grains (pasta/rice/cereals etc)

Tinned fish/meat

Fresh fruit

Tinned fruit

Fresh vegetables

Tinned vegetables

Juice

Dairy products

Dairy alternative options

Eggs

Bread

Vegan products (please specify)

Gluten free products (please specify)

Spices (please specify)

Biscuits

Chocolate

Other (please specify)

Are there any foods that you wouldn't want to see in a food shop from YAC?

Is there anything that would prevent you from accessing a YAC food shop?

Are you happy to eat food that is close to best before/ sell-by dates?

Do you feel you are currently able to meet your dietary needs?

Yes/ No

Please explain

Do you cook meals from scratch?

Yes

No

Sometimes

Is there anything that prevents you from cooking your own meals?

Time

Access to ingredients

Access to cooking equipment and facilities

Other (please specify)

Are there any meals you would like to learn how to cook?

Where does your knowledge of what is 'healthy' food come from?

School

Family members

Television (please specify)

Books (please specify)

Other

What does 'sustainable' and 'low-waste' food mean to you?

Are there certain foods that make you 'happy?' If so, please briefly explain why.

Would you be happy to discuss your relationship and views on food in more detail?

Yes / No

Is there anything else you would like to share about your experiences of accessing or not accessing food within Brighton and Hove or elsewhere?

Interview schedule:

(Please note that these will be revised and expanded upon in relation to the survey responses and ideas here are only indicative)

- Introductions and revisiting of consent
- How did you first hear about the YAC Food Market?
- When not accessing food from YAC, where do you normally get your food from?
- Are you always able to access the food you want?
- How do you normally prepare your meals?
- Are you responsible for feeding anyone else?
- What things are you looking for in a food market?
- How do you travel to YAC?
- What role does food play in your life?

INFORMATION SHEET FOR PARENTS AND CARERS

STUDY TITLE: SUSTAINABLE SOCIAL GROCERY STORES: SEEKING THE 'SOCIAL' BEHIND THE MARKET

INVITATION

Your child/a child in your care has been invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether or not they should take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

The purpose of this study is to understand more about young peoples' understanding of food within their local communities, their food-seeking behaviours and values as well as how they access and engage with the food they eat.

WHY HAS MY CHILD BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

They have been invited to participate because they have previously or currently purchased food from the YAC Food market and they are between the ages of 16-18.

DO THEY HAVE TO TAKE PART?

No! It is up to them to decide whether or not to take part. If they do decide to take part, they will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. We will also ask you as their guardian to sign a consent form. Your child is free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. They can withdraw any data they give to the study until 1st July 2022 after which we will have started the analysis. Choosing to take part in this study will have no impact on their marks, assessments or future studies.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN IF THEY TAKE PART?

They will be invited to participate in an interview which will last around 1 hour and can be held face to face or via zoom depending on their preference. With their and your consent, the discussion will be recorded and their responses will be anonymised and analysed.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART?

The primary disadvantage of participating in this study is the time taken to participate. Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any discomfort. If your child were to feel distressed by any of the topics raised, the interview can be stopped at any time and your child would be signposted to relevant support services to discuss the cause of their distress.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

By taking part in this study you are helping to expand knowledge on the role of food and food provision within your local community. This will be of potential benefit in informing the agendas of organisations concerned with food distribution within the area. Interview participants will receive a small recompense in the form of a shopping voucher for their time.

WILL INFORMATION IN THIS STUDY BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL?

All information collected will be kept strictly confidential. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity will be ensured through strict adherence to the guidelines for storing, managing and processing data set out in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018. This research project

involves the use of University of Sussex Zoom. Details of the platform's privacy notice can be found here: [Zoom Privacy Policy](#).

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF MY CHILD WANTS TO TAKE PART?

To opt in for the study, yourself and your child need to sign the consent form. Your child will then also need to be available for the 1 hour discussion, although this will be arranged at a time that suits them.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of this research study will be used to inform a number of academic pieces of work. These may include: articles in published academic journals, academic book chapters, public presentations, conferences and/or events. Copies of any research output will be made freely available to all participants, although participants should note that this process is planned to take place over a 5 year period, with data retained for the length of that period.

WHO IS ORGANISING AND FUNDING THE RESEARCH?

Research will be undertaken by members of the Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex. The project is part of a larger UKRI research study entitled 'Transforming Food Systems for Disadvantaged Communities', which is administered at the University of Reading.

WHO HAS APPROVED THIS STUDY?

The study has been improved by the Social Sciences & Arts Cross-Schools Research Ethics Committee (SSARTA) at the University of Sussex. The ethical review application numbers is [XX/XXXX/X].

CONTACT FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

If you require any additional information, please contact Dr Fawzia Mazanderani from the University of Sussex by emailing f.mazanderani@sussex.ac.uk or Dr Elaine Swan by emailing e.swan@sussex.ac.uk. If you have any questions or concerns relating to this research please contact Ruth Stirton, Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee (r.stirton@sussex.ac.uk (Chair of the C-REC who reviewed the project).

INSURANCE

The University of Sussex has insurance in place to cover its legal liabilities in respect of this study.

THANK YOU

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet. Any participation is greatly appreciated.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

STUDY TITLE: SUSTAINABLE SOCIAL GROCERY STORES: SEEKING THE ‘SOCIAL’ BEHIND THE MARKET

INVITATION

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

The purpose of this study is to understand more about young peoples’ understanding of food within their local communities, their food-seeking behaviours and values as well as how they access and engage with the food they eat.

WHY HAVE I BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

You have been invited to participate because you have previously or currently purchased food from the YAC Food market.

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

No! It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. You are however still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. You can withdraw any data you give to the study until 1st July 2022 after which we will have started the analysis. Choosing to take part in this study will have no impact on your marks, assessments or future studies.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO ME IF I TAKE PART?

You will be invited to participate in an interview which will last around 1 hour and can be held face to face or via zoom depending on your preference. With your consent, the discussion will be recorded and their responses will be anonymised and analysed.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART?

The primary disadvantage of participating in this study is the time taken to participate. Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any discomfort. If you were to feel distressed by any of the topics raised, the interview can be stopped at any time, and you can be signposted to relevant support services to discuss the cause of your distress.

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This research project involves the use of University of Sussex Zoom. Details of the platform's privacy notice can be found here: [Zoom Privacy Policy](#).

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WANT TO TAKE PART?

To opt in for the study, please agree to take part by signing the consent form and making yourself available for the 1 hour discussion, which can be arranged at a time that suits you.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of this research study will be used to inform a number of academic pieces of work. These may include: articles in published academic journals, academic book chapters, public presentations, conferences and/or events. Copies of any research output will be made freely available to all participants, although participants should note that this process is planned to take place over a 5 year period, with data retained for the length of that period.

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If you require any additional information, please contact Dr Fawzia Mazanderani from the University of Sussex by emailing f.mazanderani@sussex.ac.uk or Dr Elaine Swan by emailing e.swan@sussex.ac.uk. If you have any questions or concerns relating to this research please contact Ruth Stirton, Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee (r.stirton@sussex.ac.uk) (Chair of the C-REC who reviewed the project).

INSURANCE

The University of Sussex has insurance in place to cover its legal liabilities in respect of this study.

THANK YOU

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet. Any participation is greatly appreciated.

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS PARENTS/GUARDIANS

Title of Project: Sustainable social grocery stores: Seeking the ‘social’ behind the market

Name of Researcher and School: Dr Elaine Swan and Dr Fawzia Mazanderani

C-REC Ref no: [X]

Please tick box

- | | YES | NO |
|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I consent to _____ being involved in an interview with the researcher. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that any information that is provided is confidential, and that no information that is disclosed will lead to the identification of any individual in the reports on the project, either by the researcher or by any other party. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have read the information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that the interviews will be audio recorded for transcription purposes | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that personal data related to _____ will be used for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with data protection legislation. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <p>I understand that they can withdraw any data they give to the study until 1st July 2022 after which we will have started the analysis.</p> | | |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand participation in this research is voluntary, that the young person under my care does not have to participate in part or all of the project, and that they can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I agree for _____ to take part in the above University of Sussex research project. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

Title of Project: Sustainable social grocery stores: Seeking the 'social' behind the market

Name of Researcher and School: Dr Elaine Swan and Dr Fawzia Mazanderani

C-REC Ref no: [X]

Please tick box

YES NO

- | | | |
|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I consent to engaging in an interview with the researcher. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I understand that the interviews will be audio recorded for transcription purposes. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I understand that any information I provide is confidential, and that no information that I disclose will lead to the identification of any individual in the reports on the project, either by the researcher or by any other party. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I have read the information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I understand that my personal data will be used for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with data protection legislation. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I understand I can withdraw any data I give to the study until 1st July 2022 after which we will have started the analysis. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• I agree to take part in the above University of Sussex research project. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Explanation of Return

Dear Elaine,

Thank you for submitting your application to the Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee.

Your application requires revision and a resubmission to the committee. If you feel that we have misunderstood an aspect of your application, or you'd like to speak about the comments below before starting your resubmission, please contact tim.parkinson@sussex.ac.uk.

Please consider the points made below and resubmit your application to the committee.

1 - Please, can you add a specific date/time by which participants can no longer request their data be withdrawn from the study to the Participant Information Sheet and Consent Forms.

We have added these and resubmitted a new info and consent forms.

2 - Within the Consent Forms please can you add a clause that the interviews will be audio recorded for transcription purposes

We have added these to the two consent forms – participants and parents/guardians

3 - Please add the following sentence to the Participant Information Sheet 'if you have any questions or concerns relating to this research please contact Ruth Stirton, Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee (r.stirton@sussex.ac.uk)'.

We have done this.

4 - Please can you add a link to the Zoom privacy policy to the Participant Information Sheets.

We have added this to the info sheets.

Please include a PDF with your resubmission that states how you have addressed the above points.

Best wishes

Dr Ruth Stirton
Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts Cross-School Research Committee

Thank you, Ruth.